

Primality-testing formula using only elementary functions without Wilson's theorem

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Abstract

Using trigonometric properties, in particular sums of squares of sines and cosines, a primality-testing formula is obtained, consisting only of elementary functions and not based on Wilson's theorem.

In 1964, C. P. Willans derived a formula for generating prime numbers [2]. Several variants of this formula have been derived, some of which do not rely on Wilson's theorem, but instead use the floor function [1], a not-elementary function.

The following primality-testing formula can be used inside the Willans formula; it consists only of elementary functions and is not based on Wilson's theorem:

$$\prod_{i=2}^{n-1} \left(\frac{2}{i} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \sin^2(j \cdot n \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) \right) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{1} & \text{if } n \text{ is a prime number} \\ \mathbf{0} & \text{if } n \text{ is a composite number} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Proof

First, equation (2) is proved:

$$\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \sin^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) = \frac{i}{2} \quad (2)$$

$$\sin^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) + \cos^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) = 1$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} [\sin^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) + \cos^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i})] = \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} 1_j = i - 1$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \sin^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \cos^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) = i - 1 \quad (3)$$

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$$\cos^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) - \sin^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) = \cos(2j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i})$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} [\cos^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) - \sin^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i})] = \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \cos(2j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i})$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \cos^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \sin^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) = \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \cos(2j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) \quad (4)$$

For even i , it is clear that all the cosine terms cancel each other out, except for one (see the exaple in Figure 1). Thus, $\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \cos(2j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) = -1$.

Figure 1: Example for $\frac{\pi}{8}$

For odd i , it is necessary to consider a vector sum. In any case, the resultant is the vector lying on $\alpha = \pi$ (see the exaple in Figure 2). Thus, $\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \cos(2j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) = -1$.

Figure 2: Example for $\frac{\pi}{5}$

Therefore, in general:

$$\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \cos^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \sin^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) = -1 \quad (5)$$

Substituting in (3): $\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \sin^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \cos^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) = i + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \cos^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \sin^2(j \cdot \frac{\pi}{i})$, which gives (2).

Now, equation (6) is proved:

$$\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \sin^2(j \cdot n \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) = \frac{i}{2} \quad \text{if } n \text{ is a prime number, or coprime to } i \quad (6)$$

Since it is:

$$j \cdot n \cdot \frac{\pi}{i} = r \cdot n \cdot \frac{\pi}{i} + (j - r) \cdot n \cdot \frac{\pi}{i} \quad (7)$$

$(j - r) \cdot n \cdot \frac{\pi}{i} \neq k \cdot \pi$ ($j - r < i$ and k is an integer) if n is a prime number, or coprime to i .

Therefore, $j \cdot n \cdot \frac{\pi}{i} \not\equiv r \cdot n \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}$ ($r < j$); for each j , a different angle is obtained, and the summation, as in (2), can be constructed.

Next, it is simple to prove (8):

$$\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \sin^2(j \cdot n \cdot \frac{\pi}{i}) = 0 \quad \text{if } n \text{ is a multiple of } i \quad (8)$$

Finally, at this point, it is easy to derive (1).

References

- [1] Issam Kaddoura and Samih Abdul-Nabi. On formula to compute primes and the nth prime. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1202.4687*, 2012.
- [2] C.P. Willans. On formulae for the nth prime number. *The Mathematical Gazette*, 48(366):413–415, 1964.